

Estimating The Minimally Clinical Important Difference Of Six Minute Walk Distance In Patients With Breast Cancer- A Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women across the world. Early detection of breast cancer followed by efficient multimodality treatment shows potential improvement in quality of life. Six minute Walk test is used to assess the functional capacity and the effectiveness of treatment intervention.

Materials and Methods: 37 subjects diagnosed with breast cancer aged 18 and above were recruited. The baseline data was assessed before chemoradiation therapy and after sixteen weeks of chemoradiation therapy. The assessment included the 6MWT and EORTC QLQ C-30.

Results: MCID was calculated using anchor- and distribution-based methods. The mean decline in participants for 6MWD was 11meters. The receiver operating curve indicated a cut-off value for clinically relevant change with respect to EORTC QLQ C-30 to be 15meters (95% confidence interval) (area under curve 0.66) with sensitivity 70.6% and specificity 70%.

Discussion: 6MWT demonstrated a change of 15meters in distribution-based method. Findings also suggested that there is a correlation between functional capacity and QOL. Overall 6MWT appears to be a valuable tool to assess the functional capacity.

Conclusion: The MCID for 6MWD in breast cancer patients is 15meters. 6MWT emerges to be useful tool for planning assessment, treatment and monitoring because it exhibits significant and clear relationships with physical fitness and cancer related symptoms.

Keywords: Breast cancer, six-minute walk test, minimally clinical important difference, chemoradiation therapy, quality of life

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is most commonly diagnosed and one of the leading cancers amongst women worldwide.¹ According to the Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN), in 2020 there were 19.3 million cancer cases worldwide and with the increasing prevalence India ranked the third highest. One out of every eight female diagnosed with cancer is diagnosed to have breast cancer and every sixth death is due to breast cancer.² Breast cancer arises when there is growth of the malignant or cancer-causing cells in either ducts or lobules of the breast. Lump in the breast, change in the size of breast, fluid discharge from the nipple, dimpling of the skin

and red or scaly patch on the breast can be the signs of breast carcinoma.³ Certain risk factors associated with breast cancer includes obesity, physical inactivity, alcohol, early menarche and late menopause, family history and BRCA1/ BRCA2 gene mutation. Diagnostic methods available for cancer detection includes mammography, needle biopsy of breast, ultrasound, PET scan (positron emission tomography), MRI, including self-examination.⁴ Early intervention and treatment techniques of chemotherapy, radiation therapy, surgery and hormone therapy can lower the risks and spread of the cancer. Cancer patients undergoing CTRT treatment will often experience various side effects like nausea,

vomiting, alopecia, weight gain, sleep disturbance, fatigue and various heart related problems. These symptoms have a negative impact on their day-to-day activities and on overall quality of life. Amongst these symptoms fatigue has major impact on a person's physical, social and emotional dimension of quality of life along with other factors such as age, educational level, stage of the cancer and diagnosis of the disease itself.⁵Quality of Life (QoL) means the general wellbeing or an overall health status of an individual. Several factors related to cancer affects the QoL. It is considered as an important aspect to evaluate the QoL of an individual following any treatment regimen.⁶European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) has created several questionnaires to assess the Quality of Life of cancer patients which are available in different languages. QLQ-30 is one of the questionnaires used to study about the QoL in breast cancer patients over past week which includes 30 items containing functional scale, symptom scale and Global health status/QoL scale.⁷Six Minute Walk Test(6MWT) is an assessment tool for measuring functional capacity of an individual and can be used in breast cancer patients to map the changes after treatment regime.⁸6MWT is used as an outcome tool to assess functional capacity and has strong correlation to QOL. Minimally clinical important difference (MCID) is a clinical measure to assess the smallest change in one's treatment outcome which an individual identifies as important.⁹ Anticancer treatments like chemoradiation therapy induce complications such as decline in cardiopulmonary fitness and has major impact on QoL in patients with breast cancer. The present study aimed to estimate the MCID of 6MWD in patients with breast cancer undergoing chemoradiation therapy as there are no studies reporting MCID in 6MWT for breast cancer patients. However, understanding and appreciating the minimal changes will help in decision making regarding the intervention and its effectiveness. Thus, interpretation of the functional changes will guide the clinical management of breast cancer patients.

OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this study is to estimate the minimal clinically important difference (MCID) of the six-minute walk distance (6MWD) in patients with breast cancer. The secondary objectives are to evaluate the EORTC QLQ-C30 questionnaire at baseline (pre-treatment) and after 16 weeks of chemotherapy and to correlate its physical domain with 6MWD, as well as to determine whether the six-minute walk test serves as an indicator of health measures in breast cancer patients receiving chemoradiation therapy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Nicole Tubiana-Mathieu** et al.¹⁰ evaluated whether the six-minute walk test (6MWT) could individualize exercise intensity in 138 breast cancer patients undergoing adjuvant therapy. Heart rate during 6MWT showed a significant correlation with ventilatory threshold heart rate from CPET (ICC = 0.69; $r = 0.70$; $p < 0.001$), independent of age and BMI. The study concluded that 6MWT heart rate can be used to prescribe exercise intensity before and after treatment.
2. **Catherine L. Granger**¹¹ determined the Minimal Important Difference (MID) of the 6MWT in lung cancer patients assessed at baseline and 8–10 weeks. A mean decline of 43 m in 6MWD was observed. Distribution-based analysis identified an MID ranging from 22 m to 32 m.
3. A systematic review and meta-analysis by **Jasna But Hadzic** et al.¹² (2007–2020) evaluated the six-minute walk test (6MWT) in breast cancer survivors (BCS), including 21 studies (9 RCTs, 8 cohort, 4 cross-sectional) with 1084 BCS. Results showed that healthy individuals walked significantly longer distances than BCS (589.9 m vs 477 m; $p < 0.001$). The 6-minute walk distance (6MWD) was significantly associated with BMI ($p < 0.001$) but not age ($p = 0.070$). Even after BMI adjustment, healthy individuals performed better. The study concluded that 6MWT is a useful measure for assessing

and monitoring cardiorespiratory fitness in BCS.

4. **Miriam A.G. Sprangers**¹³ conducted a multicounty study (Dutch, Spanish, and American populations) to evaluate the validity and reliability of the EORTC breast cancer-specific quality of life questionnaire. The 23-item tool assessed treatment-related effects such as body image and sexuality, administered at different treatment stages across populations. Multitrait analysis showed acceptable item-convergent validity (≥ 0.40) across key domains, while reliability (Cronbach's alpha) ranged from moderate to high, highest in the American sample. The questionnaire also distinguished between clinical groups based on disease and treatment factors. The study concluded that the tool is valid and reliable for assessing quality of life in breast cancer patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Study Subjects:

The study protocol was approved by Father Mullers institutional ethics committee and patients diagnosed with breast cancer scheduled for chemo-radiation therapy were screened for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients willing to participate were asked to sign written consent.

Study Design:

Participants performed 6MWT at baseline (pre-treatment) and after 16 weeks of CTRT. The Quality of Life over the past week was assessed by EORTC QLQ C-30 at baseline and after 16 weeks.

Outcome measures:

6MWT was assessed according to the guidelines of American Thoracic Society. The subjects were asked to walk a 30-meter corridor and before beginning and at the end of the test all the vitals (heart rate, blood pressure, SpO₂ and rate of perceived exertion using Borg Scale) were measured.

EORTC QLQ-30 questionnaire form was provided to the participants in their preferred language at both the points (pre and post CTRT) containing 30 items, 24 of which are aggregated into 9 multi-item scales: 5

functioning scales (physical, role, cognitive, emotional, and social); 3 symptom scales (fatigue, pain, and nausea and/or vomiting); and 1 global health status scale. Responses were recorded based on the Likert scale mentioned. The remaining six single items assess symptoms of dyspnoea, appetite loss (AP), sleep disturbance, constipation, diarrhoea, and financial impact.

Change in the PF domain of the EORTC-QLQ-C30 questionnaire was used as an anchor to determine whether participants noticed improvement, deterioration or no change in their PF from pre-treatment to post-treatment. Change in the PF domain of three or more points is considered clinically relevant.

Statistical Analysis:

Data was coded and entered in SPSS software. Paired t test was used for determining the change in 6MWD and EORTC QLQ-C30 from baseline and after 16 weeks of chemoradiation therapy. Anchor and Distribution methods used for determining MCID. Mean, Standard Deviation and ROC analysis was done to find out the cut-off for 6MWD. p value < 0.05 is considered significant.

RESULTS

40 participants were enrolled and allocated to the study. Three were lost to follow-up, and 37 participants were analysed with stage 2 and stage 3 cancer. 24 subjects received Chemo-Radiation Therapy whereas 14 received only chemotherapy. Correlation between parameters 6MWD and EORTC-30 was done using paired t test for pre and post (16 weeks) of CTRT. The results were presented in mean, standard deviation and mean difference (Table 1) which shows no significant correlation seen pre and post of CTRT and 6MWD. Functional scale of EORTC QLQ-30 showed significant change in cognitive function with $p=0.015$. PF domain also showed significant change with $p=0.02$. Emotional and role function pre and post CTRT did not show any change. In symptom scales of EORTC QLQ-30 appetite loss showed significant change with $p=0.044$.

The mean for 6MWD from baseline to post was shown to be 11mts CTRT with standard Deviation 59.3 meters (Table 2.A). For EORTC QLQ c-30 quality of life median of 3 was considered as the MCID. Anchor based

method was used to categorize the subjects into deteriorated and not deteriorated. An increase in the score by 3 and more post CTRT compared to pre CTRT participants were categorized as deteriorated and the score less than 3 points categorized as not deteriorated. Out of 37 participants 17 were not deteriorated whereas 20 participants were deteriorated post

16 weeks of CTRT (Table 2.B). Distribution based method was used to obtain the cut off value for MCID of 6MWT with respect to EORTC QLQ C-30 based on deteriorated and not deteriorated using ROC analysis. AUC is 0.66, cut off value is found to be change of 15mts with sensitivity 70.6% and specificity 70% (Figure 1, Table 3).

Table 1 (A): Correlation Between Parameters (Pre And Post Sixteen Weeks Of Ctrt)

Parameter		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	Change(%)	Paired t test p value	
6 MWD	Pre	40	375.75	90.72	6.83	1.82	0.128	NS
	Post	37	368.92	93.18				
EORTC-30	Pre	40	61.53	10.20	-1.53	2.49	0.088	NS
	Post	37	63.05	8.20				

Table 1(B): Correlation Between Parameters (Pre And Post Sixteen Weeks Of Ctrt) Of Eortc-30 QLQ

Parameter			N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	Change (%)	Paired t test p value	
FUNCTIONAL SCALES	Cognitive Function	Pre	40	3.05	0.99	-0.54	17.86	0.015	Sig
		Post	37	3.59	1.36				
	Emotional function	Pre	40	7.73	2.41	-0.22	2.86	0.393	NS
		Post	37	7.95	2.37				
	PF Domain	Pre	40	8.60	1.97	-0.59	6.85	0.022	Sig
		Post	37	9.19	1.97				
	Role Function	Pre	40	5.00	1.04	-0.05	1.08	0.457	NS
		Post	37	5.05	1.15				
	Social Function	Pre	40	4.73	1.48	-0.46	9.82	0.008	HS
		Post	37	5.19	1.33				

Table 1(B): Continued.

Parameter			N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	Change (%)	Paired t test p value	
SYMPTOM SCALES	Appetite Loss	Pre	40	1.58	0.78	-0.29	18.40	0.044	Sig
		Post	37	1.86	0.79				
	Constipation	Pre	40	1.43	0.68	-0.01	0.52	0.864	NS
		Post	37	1.43	0.60				
	Diarrhoea	Pre	40	1.38	0.63	0.10	7.62	0.581	NS
		Post	37	1.27	0.61				
	Dyspnoea	Pre	40	1.13	0.33	-0.15	12.91	0.096	NS
		Post	37	1.27	0.61				
Fatigue	Pre	40	6.58	1.52					

	Financial difficulties	Post	37	6.95	2.12	-0.37	5.64	0.296	NS
		Pre	40	2.43	0.98				
	Insomnia	Post	37	2.59	0.83	-0.17	6.99	0.196	NS
		Pre	40	1.88	0.61				
	Nausea Vomiting	Post	37	2.89	1.33	-0.12	4.21	0.673	NS
		Pre	40	2.78	1.21				
	Pain	Post	37	4.16	1.54	-0.06	1.52	0.775	NS
		Pre	40	4.10	1.41				

Table1(B): Continued.

Parameter		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	Change(%)	Paired t test p value	
GLOBAL QOL	Pre	40	8.78	1.93	0.15	1.75	0.439	NS
	Post	37	8.62	2.15				

Table 2 (A): MCID of 6MWD and EORTC-30 QLQ (Pre-Post)

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	IQR	
				Percentile 25	Percentile 75
6 MWD(Pre-Post)	11.35	59.31	20.00	-20.00	40.00
EORTC-30(Pre-Post)	-2.00	9.11	-3.00	-10.00	2.00

Table2 (B): Comparison of change in distance according to change in EORTC-30 QLQ

EORTC-30-change categorised		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	IQR		Mann Whitney test p value
						Lower	Upper	
6 MWD(Pre-Post)	Not deteriorated	17	-7.1	55.3	-10.0	-20.0	25.0	0.000, HS
	Deteriorated	20	27.0	59.4	30.0	-20.0	67.5	

Figure 1: ROC ANALYSIS

Table 3: Change in 6MWD from baseline to follow-up, grouped as deteriorated and not deteriorated according to change in EORTCQLQ-C30 PF domain

Deteriorated if more than or Equal To 3	Sensitivity	1 - Specificity	Specificity
-191.0000	0.000	0.000	1.000
-130.0000	.059	0.000	1.000
-60.0000	.059	.100	0.900
-45.0000	.059	.150	0.850
-35.0000	.059	.200	0.800
-25.0000	.176	.250	0.750
-15.0000	.353	.250	0.750
-5.0000	.529	.250	0.750
5.0000	.588	.250	0.750
15.0000	.706	.300	0.700
25.0000	.765	.450	0.550
35.0000	.882	.600	0.400
45.0000	.941	.650	0.350
55.0000	.941	.700	0.300
65.0000	.941	.750	0.250
75.0000	.941	.850	0.150
90.0000	1.000	.900	0.100
135.0000	1.000	.950	0.050
171.0000	1.000	1.000	0.000

DISCUSSION

Breast cancer remains a major contributor to morbidity and mortality among women. Modifiable risk factors such as obesity, physical inactivity, and alcohol consumption highlight the importance of lifestyle management in prevention and survivorship.¹⁴The disease and its treatment significantly affect physical health, making rehabilitation and physiotherapy essential components of care.

The present study aimed to estimate the Minimal Clinically Important Difference (MCID) of the 6-Minute Walk Test (6MWT) in patients with breast cancer undergoing chemoradiation therapy. The 6MWT is a simple, feasible, and widely accepted tool for assessing functional capacity. Thirty-seven participants were assessed at baseline and after 16 weeks of chemoradiation therapy. The findings demonstrated that a change of 15 meters with distribution-based method represents the smallest clinically meaningful difference, with a sensitivity of 70.6% and specificity of 70%.

Quality of life was assessed using the EORTC QLQ-C30. Patients were categorized as

deteriorated or non-deteriorated based on a ≥ 3 -point change in scores. Significant changes were observed in the physical function ($p=0.02$) and cognitive function ($p=0.04$) domains. These findings suggest an association between functional capacity and quality of life.

Similar findings were reported by Catherine L Granger in lung cancer patients, where moderate correlation was observed between changes in 6MWD and physical function domain scores ($r=0.57$, $p<0.0001$).¹¹Previous research in breast cancer populations has also demonstrated relationships between 6MWD and physical fitness, fatigue, anxiety, body composition, and overall quality of life.

Overall, the 6MWT appears to be a valuable tool for assessing functional capacity, while the EORTC QLQ-C30 effectively evaluates quality of life in breast cancer patients. Given the established benefits of exercise on physical fitness, fatigue reduction, and overall wellbeing, the observed MCID in this study further supports the clinical relevance of functional assessment in this population.

However this study indicates fair accuracy, suggesting that the measure has limited ability to distinguish between deteriorated and non-

deteriorated patients. The study population demonstrates heterogeneity between patients receiving chemoradiotherapy (CRT) and those undergoing chemotherapy alone. These treatment modalities may differ in their physiological impact, side effects, and recovery patterns, potentially influencing 6MWD outcomes and the estimated MCID.

CONCLUSION

The MCID for 6MWD in breast cancer patients is 15 meters. This estimation may be useful in clinical interpretation of data particularly in interventional study. 6MWT emerges to be a useful tool for planning assessment, treatment and monitoring because it exhibits significant and clear relationships with physical fitness and cancer-related symptoms. 6MWT protocol may be used as a guide for recommending exercise training to improve the overall functional capacity in breast cancer patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

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Ethical Clearance:

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